

DEVELOPING STRATEGIES FOR STRAWBERRY AGROTOURISM IN SEMBALUN DISTRICT, EAST LOMBOK, INDONESIA

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Abstract: The objectives of this study are to: (1) determine appropriate strategies for strawberry agritourism in Sembalun District, East Lombok Regency; and (2) establish priority strategies for the development of strawberry agritourism in Sembalun District, East Lombok Regency. The respondents of this study consisted of 29 individuals selected through purposive sampling across five villages, along with six key informants comprising experts in relevant fields. Data were analyzed by SWOT and QSPM analyses. The analysis results revealed that: (1) The suitable development strategy for strawberry agritourism in Sembalun District is a growth-oriented strategy (aggressive strategy). The S-O (Strengths-Opportunities) strategy consists of four alternative strategies. (2) The top-priority strategy for developing strawberry agritourism in Sembalun District is to develop an integrated agritourism concept by incorporating various activities and additional facilities to attract more visitors and extend their length of stay. The novelty of this study lies in the key internal and external factors influencing the development of strawberry agrotourism in Sembalun, with a particular emphasis on the importance of implementing an integrated agrotourism concept. Additionally, this study employs SWOT and QSPM analyses, which have proven to be effective tools in formulating and determining appropriate development strategies.

Keywords: Agritourism, Strawberry, SWOT Analysis, QSPM Priority.

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia, as an agrarian country rich in natural resources, possesses vast land availability and significant prospects for developing various enterprises, particularly in the agricultural sector (Kurniasanti, 2019). The agricultural sector plays a vital role in absorbing labor and serves as the primary source of income for the majority of rural households. Despite its importance, the functions and benefits of rural and agricultural areas are often underappreciated (Budiarti et al., 2013).

As an agrarian country with extensive rural lands, Indonesia holds great potential for developing agrarian activities ranging from cultivation to post-harvest processing, offering a unique attraction for tourism. This condition can be leveraged to enhance the national economy, which is subsequently developed into the concept of agritourism by integrating agronomy activities with the tourism sector (Kurniasanti, 2019).

The tourism sector plays a strategic role in promoting economic growth, particularly in regions endowed with unique natural and cultural resources (Fadilla, 2024). Tourism development not only contributes to increasing regional income but also creates employment opportunities and new business prospects for local communities (Ismowati et al., 2022). One of the tourism models that has grown rapidly in recent years is agritourism, which integrates agricultural activities with tourist visits (Muzaqi & Hanum, 2020). This model is considered capable of adding value to agricultural products and extending the local economic value chain (Nurjati, 2021).

Sembalun District, located in East Lombok Regency, is one of the regions with significant potential for agritourism development, particularly strawberry agritourism (Haryanto & Sarjan, 2025). According to Rasmilah (2022), based on its geographic conditions at high altitude and cool climate, this area is highly suitable for strawberry cultivation. In addition,

the beautiful natural scenery and the presence of Mount Rinjani as the main tourist attraction position Sembalun as a leading destination in West Nusa Tenggara (Pradnyana et al., 2022). Strawberry farming practiced by local communities has even attracted both domestic and international tourists who seek the experience of picking fruit directly from the farm (Akbar et al., 2024).

Despite its considerable potential, the development of strawberry agritourism in Sembalun still faces various challenges (Wijayanti & Nursalim, 2023). The main issues encountered include the suboptimal condition of supporting tourism facilities, such as accessibility, tourism infrastructure, and promotional efforts (Kurniadi, 2022). According to Wispandono et al. (2022), farmer institutions in agritourism remain informal and poorly organized, making it difficult to implement large-scale and sustainable development initiatives. The capacity of human resources, particularly in aspects of tourism service and management, is also still limited (Nurrahman et al., 2021).

The local government has made efforts to promote the development of the agritourism area in Sembalun through various programs, such as training, provision of agricultural equipment assistance, and the development of basic infrastructure (Wati, 2022). However, the implementation of these programs has not yet been integrated into a comprehensive, data-driven development strategy (Permanasari et al., 2020). Therefore, systematic strategic planning is required to ensure that the direction of agritourism development aligns with the actual potential and conditions on the ground (Pira et al., 2025). Such planning needs to consider various internal and external factors influencing the development of this sector (Widiantini et al., 2024).

This study aims to: (1) determine the development strategies that can be implemented for strawberry agritourism in Sembalun District, East Lombok Regency; and (2) establish the priority strategies for developing strawberry agritourism in Sembalun District, East Lombok Regency. This research serves as an informative resource that provides a comprehensive overview of the potential, challenges, and development strategies of strawberry agritourism in Sembalun District, thereby offering valuable insights for policymakers, business practitioners, academics, and researchers in decision-making processes and further studies.

II. METHODS

This study employed a descriptive approach using a survey method. This approach was chosen as it is appropriate for describing the actual conditions in the field regarding the development of strawberry agritourism in Sembalun District. The primary research location encompassed five villages actively engaged in strawberry agritourism activities. These villages include Sembalun Lawang, Sembalun Bumbung, Sajang, Bilok Petung, and Sembalun Timba Gading.

Respondents were selected purposively based on the main criterion of being farmers who also manage strawberry agritourism activities on their farms. A total of 29 respondents were involved, deemed sufficiently representative to provide an overview of agritourism development in the area. Additionally, six key informants participated in the study, consisting of government officials, academics, agricultural extension officers, and agritourism managers. Data collection techniques included observation and structured interviews.

Data analysis was conducted in several stages. The first stage involved identifying internal and external factors using a SWOT matrix. SWOT analysis was employed to identify the strategic position of agritourism development based on strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (Damayanti et al., 2025). Internal factors included strengths such as natural advantages and farmer community support, as well as weaknesses such as limited infrastructure and human resources. External factors included opportunities such as the trend of educational tourism and government policy support, and threats such as competition among destinations and the impacts of climate change. The strategic position was then determined based on the SWOT quadrant. In this stage, indicator measurements for weights ranged from 0.0 to 1.0, reflecting the relative importance of each component to the success of agritourism. Meanwhile, ratings ranged from 1 to 4, indicating the degree of influence of agritourism on these key factors. Subsequently, the weighted score was calculated by multiplying the weight and rating, yielding a score used to formulate alternative strategies.

The second stage involved formulating alternative strategies based on the combination of SWOT factors. These alternatives were further analyzed using the QSPM method to determine the priority strategies. QSPM was utilized to assess and select the most appropriate strategy based on the attractiveness of available alternatives by applying weights and scores to the key factors previously identified (Sagala et al., 2025). The indicators used in this stage were measured on a scale from 1 to 5, indicating the level of influence of each alternative strategy derived from the SWOT analysis results. The final output was a prioritized sequence of agritourism development strategies deemed most relevant and with the highest potential for successful implementation in Sembalun District.

This method provides a systematic and objective framework in strategic decision-making by quantifying qualitative data into numerical scores, thus minimizing subjective bias and enhancing the accuracy of the chosen strategy.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Strawberry agritourism in Sembalun offers various attractive activities for tourists, including the experience of picking strawberries directly from the farm, tasting fresh strawberries, and participating in educational sessions on organic strawberry cultivation techniques. This not only adds value to the agricultural sector but also enhances the tourism appeal of the region. The development of strawberry agritourism in Sembalun has provided significant benefits for the local community. Several farmers have begun shifting towards agritourism-based farming models, which have not only increased their income but also created new employment opportunities in the tourism and service sectors.

Analysis of Internal Factors (Strengths and Weaknesses) and External Factors (Opportunities and Threats) of Strawberry Agritourism

Internal Factors of the Strawberry Agritourism

The internal factors of strawberry agritourism in Sembalun include aspects within the destination that influence its sustainability and competitiveness. These factors encompass elements of production, tourism services, and supporting facilities. This analysis is essential to understand the strengths and weaknesses in the development of strawberry agritourism. By identifying internal factors such as the quality of strawberry production, the efficiency of tourism services, and the availability of adequate facilities, stakeholders can devise strategies to enhance the strengths and address the weaknesses. This will help ensure the long-term success and competitiveness of the destination.

Table 1. Internal Factors of Strawberry Agritourism

No	Strengths	No	Weaknesses
1	The location of the land is suitable for strawberry agrotourism	1	Lack of information about the strawberry season
2	The uniqueness of strawberries as an attraction for agrotourism	2	High risk of strawberry damage
3	The service in strawberry agrotourism is very satisfying	3	Suboptimal marketing
4	The entrance ticket price is affordable	4	Lack of information about the strawberry season
5	The supporting facilities for strawberry agrotourism are adequate	5	Lack of interesting photo spots
6	The quality of the strawberries produced is good and distinctive		

External Factors of the Strawberry Agritourism

External factors in strawberry agrotourism represent elements that may act as opportunities or threats in the development of strawberry agrotourism in Sembalun District (Naïla, 2022). These factors, which lie beyond the direct control of stakeholders, can substantially influence the strategic direction and overall success of strawberry agrotourism initiatives. Opportunities—such as growing demand for nature-based and educational tourism, along with advancements in digital marketing—offer potential to attract a broader visitor base. Conversely, challenges including competition from similar destinations, climate change, and shifting consumer preferences must be strategically managed to ensure the sustainable development of strawberry agrotourism.

Table 2. External Factors of Strawberry Agritourism

No	Opportunities	No	Threats
1	Sembalun is a tourism destination area	1	Emergence of similar agritourism ventures
2	Increasing interest in nature-based and educational tourism	2	The number of new tourist attraction developments
3	Strawberry agrotourism attracts visitors from various backgrounds	3	The risk of climate change and unpredictable weather
4	Ease of promotion through digital media	4	The shift in farmers' interests toward cultivating other agricultural commodities
5	Advancement in information technology		

Analysis of IFAS and EFAS Matrices

a. Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE) Matrix Analysis

The Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE) Matrix is an analytical tool utilized to assess the strengths and weaknesses within a business venture, including the strawberry agrotourism in Sembalun. This matrix identifies influential internal factors, subsequently assigning weights and ratings to determine their level of significance. The IFE matrix also provides a quantitative assessment of how well strawberry agrotourism is leveraging its strengths and addressing its weaknesses, allowing for more informed decision-making. In the context of agrotourism, it helps identify key areas for improvement, whether it be in service quality, infrastructure, or product offerings. The IFE matrix employed in this study is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Matrix IFE

Strategic Internal Factors	Weight	Rating	Score	Remarks
Strengths:				
The location of the land is suitable for strawberry agrotourism	0,099	3,586	0,355	Maintain
The uniqueness of strawberries as an attraction for agrotourism	0,087	3,379	0,295	Maintain
The service in strawberry agrotourism is very satisfying	0,093	3,414	0,317	Maintain
The entrance ticket price is affordable	0,093	3,310	0,309	Maintain
The supporting facilities for strawberry agrotourism are adequate	0,091	3,621	0,330	Maintain
The quality of the strawberries produced is good and distinctive	0,090	3,345	0,301	Maintain
Total	0,553	20,655	1,906	
Weaknesses:				
Lack of information about the strawberry season	0,090	2,034	0,183	Improve
High risk of strawberry damage	0,093	2,138	0,198	Improve
Suboptimal marketing	0,088	2,103	0,186	Improve
Lack of information about the strawberry season	0,087	2,034	0,177	Improve
Lack of interesting photo spots	0,089	2,069	0,184	Improve
Total	0,447	10,379	0,927	
Total Internal Factors	1,000		2,959	

The analysis of internal strategy factors for strawberry agrotourism in Sembalun indicates that the main strengths lie in the highly supportive land location, adequate supporting facilities, satisfactory service, and affordable entrance fees. With a total strength score of 1.906, this shows that these internal aspects have made a positive contribution to supporting the development of agrotourism.

Conversely, the weaknesses faced by strawberry agrotourism include the high risk of fruit damage, suboptimal marketing strategies, lack of attractive photo spots, and insufficient information regarding the strawberry season. The total weakness score of 0.927 indicates that while these issues can still be addressed, they need to be improved promptly in order to enhance competitiveness.

Overall, the total internal factor score of 2.959 indicates that the internal conditions of strawberry agrotourism in Sembalun are strong enough to be further developed. The existing strengths must be consistently maintained, while weaknesses must be addressed through strategies for improving information, digital promotion, as well as developing infrastructure and the aesthetics of the area. These efforts will support the sustainability of the agrowisata stroberi and attract more tourists to Sembalun's strawberry agrotourism. By focusing on enhancing these areas, Sembalun's strawberry agrotourism can achieve sustainable growth and increase its competitiveness in the market.

b. Analysis of the EFAS Matrix

External factor evaluation is a step to plan and direct the actions that will be taken by agrotourism, based on the development of external factors that influence the agrotourism destination (Ramzah, 2019). This process helps in identifying and understanding how external variables, such as market trends, competitor activities, technological advancements, and changes in consumer preferences, can impact the strategic direction of agrotourism. The EFAS matrix in this study can be seen in Table 4, which visually represents the influence of each external factor on the strawberry agrotourism's performance.

Table 4. Matrix EFE

Strategic External Factors	Weight	Rating	Score	Remarks
Opportunities:				
Sembalun is a tourism destination area	0,119	3,483	0,415	utilized
Increasing interest in nature-based and educational tourism	0,109	3,310	0,362	utilized
Strawberry agrotourism attracts visitors from various backgrounds	0,113	3,379	0,383	utilized
Ease of promotion through digital media	0,106	3,586	0,379	utilized
Advancement in information technology	0,113	3,276	0,369	utilized
Total	0,560	17,034	1,909	
Threats:				
Emergence of similar agritourism ventures	0,116	1,862	0,215	other alternatives
The number of new tourist attraction developments	0,110	2,000	0,221	other alternatives
The risk of climate change and unpredictable weather	0,108	1,966	0,213	other alternatives
The shift in farmers' interests toward cultivating other agricultural commodities	0,105	1,931	0,203	other alternatives
Total	0,440	7,759	0,852	
Total External Factors	1,000		3,121	

The analysis of external strategy factors shows that strawberry agrotourism in Sembalun has significant opportunities for development. Its location within a tourism and educational area, the enthusiasm of visitors from various backgrounds, and the ease of promotion through digital media provide strong potential for growth. Based on these opportunity factors, this agrotourism destination can strengthen its position in reaching a wider market, resulting in an opportunity score of 1.909.

However, there are several threats that must be considered, such as the emergence of new tourist destinations, the increasing development of similar agrotourism sites, the risks of climate change and unpredictable weather, as well as the tendency of farmers to shift to other agricultural commodities—all of which may potentially disrupt the continuity of strawberry agrotourism. Although the threat score of 0.852 is relatively lower than the opportunity score, these factors still require attention and proactive mitigation.

With a total external factor score of 3.121, it can be concluded that the external conditions support the development of strawberry agrotourism in Sembalun. The existing opportunities must be optimized through digital promotion strategies and collaboration with other tourism stakeholders. Meanwhile, emerging threats can be anticipated through product innovation, service quality improvement, and sustainable approaches to maintaining farmers' commitment to agrotourism.

Internal-External (IE) Matrix Analysis

The Internal-External (IE) Matrix is a strategic analysis tool used to evaluate the internal and external factors influencing the development of strawberry agrotourism in Sembalun. This matrix identifies the agrotourism's position based on the total internal factor score derived from the Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE) analysis, which is plotted on the X-axis, and the external factors from the External Factor Evaluation (EFE) analysis, which are plotted on the Y-axis.

SWOT Diagram

The SWOT diagram (Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threats) is an analytical tool used to evaluate the strategic condition of strawberry agrotourism in Sembalun by considering internal and external factors that influence its development.

The internal analysis coordinate is obtained by subtracting the total strength score from the total weakness score, which is $1.906 - 0.927 = 0.979$. Furthermore, the external analysis coordinate is calculated by subtracting the total threat score from the total opportunity score, which is $1.909 - 0.852 = 1.057$. The result of this calculation shows that the SWOT coordinate point is located at position (0.979; 1.057). This position illustrates the strategic condition of strawberry agrotourism in Sembalun within the SWOT matrix, which can then be used as a basis for formulating appropriate development strategies to improve the competitiveness and sustainability of the tourism destination, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. SWOT Diagram

Based on the SWOT analysis, strawberry agrotourism in Sembalun is positioned in Quadrant I, which reflects a highly favorable condition. In this position, an aggressive growth strategy is highly appropriate, such as tourism product innovation, service quality improvement, and optimization of digital promotion. This strategy enables agrotourism to grow rapidly by leveraging internal strengths and responding optimally to external opportunities.

Meanwhile, if the agrotourism were positioned in Quadrants II, III, or IV, the strategies applied must be adjusted according to each respective condition. In Quadrant II, a diversification strategy is required to minimize the impact of threats by creating product variations and building partnerships. In Quadrants III and IV, improvement and defensive strategies are needed, focusing on enhancing internal quality and operational efficiency to address weaknesses and external challenges.

SWOT Matrix Analysis

The SWOT analysis is used in this study to evaluate the development strategy of strawberry agrotourism in Sembalun District by identifying its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. This method was chosen because it provides a comprehensive overview of the internal and external conditions of the agrotourism, thereby facilitating the formulation of appropriate strategies. The results of the SWOT analysis serve as the basis for determining strategic steps to enhance competitiveness, strengthen advantages, and anticipate challenges in the development of strawberry agrotourism. It was found that the alternative development strategy for strawberry agrotourism in Sembalun District, East Lombok Regency, based on SWOT analysis, results in an S-O (Strength-Opportunity) strategy with the following explanation:

a. S-O Strategies

- i. Updating visitor activities by developing educational tour packages based on strawberry agrotourism with modern facilities and high-quality services.
- ii. Enhance the promotion and marketing system by utilizing digital media and information technology to help agrotourism managers reach more tourists.
- iii. Expanding partnership networks with travel agencies, hotels, and government institutions to increase tourist visits.
- iv. Develop an integrated agrotourism concept by adding various activities and additional facilities to attract tourists and extend their length of stay.

b. W-O Strategies

- i. Educate tourists about the strawberry season and optimize marketing strategies through digital media and on-site information.
- ii. Implement post-harvest technology to reduce fruit damage and support the appeal of educational tourism.
- iii. Improve road access to the farms through collaboration with relevant stakeholders and add attractive photo spots to enhance the location's appeal.

c. S-T Strategies

- i. Develop innovations in tour packages to differentiate from competitors.
- ii. Improve infrastructure and supporting facilities, including better road access and spacious parking areas to enhance visitor comfort and reduce transportation barriers.
- iii. Increase the resilience of strawberry crops to weather changes through the application of modern agricultural technology.
- iv. Provide incentives to local farmers to maintain strawberry cultivation by offering profitable partnership systems and guaranteed market access for their harvests.

d. W-T Strategies

- i. Develop training programs for farmers to maintain their commitment to strawberry cultivation despite the temptation to switch to other commodities.
- ii. Improve management quality and develop product diversification strategies to remain competitive with other tourist destinations.
- iii. Develop community-based tourism packages to retain farmers and prevent them from switching to other commodities.

QSPM Matrix Analysis

The QSPM (Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix) is used in this study to evaluate and determine the priority of development strategies for strawberry agrotourism in Sembalun District objectively, based on the previously analyzed SWOT factors. Each of the four main S-O strategies was analyzed using the QSPM matrix by calculating the Total Attractiveness Score (TAS), derived from the weight and attractiveness score of each strategic factor. The strategy with the highest TAS is considered the top priority and is recommended for implementation in the sustainable and targeted development of strawberry agrotourism.

Table 5. Ranking of Strategic Alternatives

No.	Alternative Strategy	TAS Score	Ranking
Strategy 1	Updating visitor activities by developing educational tour packages based on strawberry agrotourism with modern facilities and high-quality services.	8,195	2
Strategy 2	Enhance the promotion and marketing system by utilizing digital media and information technology to help agrotourism managers reach more tourists.	7,373	4
Strategy 3	Expanding partnership networks with travel agencies, hotels, and government institutions to increase tourist visits.	7,613	3
Strategy 4	Develop an integrated agrotourism concept by adding various activities and additional facilities to attract tourists and extend their length of stay.	8,215	1

Based on the results of the Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM) calculation, the first alternative strategy obtained a Total Attractiveness Score (TAS) of 8.195, while the fourth strategy achieved the highest score of 8.215. This indicates that both are the most attractive strategies to implement in the development of strawberry agrotourism in Sembalun District. The fourth strategy focuses on developing an integrated agrotourism concept that includes additional activities, facilities, and supporting attractions such as educational tours, strawberry-based culinary experiences, and nature-based accommodations. This strategy is capable of leveraging almost all available strengths and opportunities while comprehensively addressing internal and external challenges, thereby creating a more complete tourism experience and increasing visitors' length of stay.

Meanwhile, the first strategy, which aims to revamp visitor activities through the development of educational tourism packages with modern facilities and high-quality services, is also considered a highly potential option. This strategy excels in enhancing the added value of agrotourism through an education-based approach, excellent service, and quality products. The second strategy (TAS = 7.373) and the third strategy (TAS = 7.613), although not as high as the first two, still demonstrate competitive attractiveness scores. However, based on the overall TAS results, the fourth strategy is more strongly recommended as the main priority in the development of strawberry agrotourism, as it is considered the most effective in improving competitiveness, sustainability, and the integration of the tourism sector with existing local potential.

The contribution of this study lies in the strategic development of local agrotourism. This research reveals that the integration of internal and external strategic factors is crucial for enhancing the sustainability and competitiveness of strawberry agrotourism in Sembalun. The findings emphasize the importance of implementing an integrated agrotourism concept—combining agricultural services, education, recreation, and accommodation—as a key driver to increase tourist visits and extend their length of stay. While previous studies generally employed only a single analysis, this study integrates both perspectives using SWOT and QSPM analyses to generate prioritized strategies for implementation. The novelty of this research lies in the identification of key success factors and the application of a combined analytical approach that not only identifies but also ranks the most effective strategies for agrotourism growth. This approach offers a strategic framework that can serve as a guideline for policymakers, agrotourism managers, and local stakeholders in designing a sustainable and competitive tourism model.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and the discussion presented in the previous sections, several important conclusions can be drawn regarding the development of strawberry agrotourism in Sembalun District. These conclusions are outlined as follows:

1. The appropriate strategy for strawberry agrotourism to be implemented in Sembalun District is an aggressive growth-oriented strategy (Growth Oriented Strategy), with the alternative S-O Strategy, namely maintaining strengths by utilizing existing opportunities through the following: (1) Updating visitor activities by developing educational tourism packages based on strawberry agrotourism with modern facilities and high-quality services, (2) Enhancing promotional and marketing systems by utilizing digital media and information technology to enable strawberry agrotourism managers to reach more tourists, (3) Expanding partnership networks with travel agents, hotels, and the government to increase tourist visits, and (4) Developing an integrated agrotourism concept by adding various activities and additional facilities to attract tourists and extend their length of stay.
2. The prioritized strawberry agrotourism development strategies to be implemented in Sembalun District, East Lombok Regency, based on their ranking are as follows: (1) Developing an integrated agrotourism concept by adding various activities and additional facilities to attract tourists and extend their length of stay, (2) Updating visitor activities by developing educational tourism packages based on strawberry agrotourism with modern facilities and high-quality services, (3) Expanding partnership networks with travel agents, hotels, and the government to increase tourist visits, and (4) Enhancing promotional and marketing systems by utilizing digital media and information technology to enable strawberry agrotourism managers to reach more tourists. The novelty of this study lies in the identification of key internal and external factors influencing the development of strawberry agrotourism in Sembalun, with a particular emphasis on the importance of implementing an integrated agrotourism concept. Additionally, this study employs SWOT and QSPM analyses, which have proven to be effective tools in formulating and determining appropriate development strategies.

Recommendation

Based on the research results, the following recommendations can be made:

1. For strawberry agrotourism business actors, it is recommended to integrate technology into the marketing process, particularly digital-based promotion, as an effort to enhance the marketing of strawberry agrotourism. One alternative that can be utilized is the optimization of social media platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube to showcase the beauty of the strawberry farms, visitor testimonials, and the educational tourism packages offered. This aims to attract tourists from various segments and broaden market reach.
2. It is recommended that farmers and agrotourism managers begin to implement modern cultivation technologies such as greenhouses. This will help maintain stable strawberry production so that fruit quality remains high and the strawberry-picking activities by visitors are not disrupted.

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